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Oral delivery of biologics for precision medicine

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Precision medicine, oral drug delivery, peptide/protein delivery, polynucleotide delivery, colonic drug delivery

Abstract

The emerging field of precision medicine is rapidly growing, fostered by the advances in genome mapping and molecular diagnosis. **In general**, the translation of these advances into precision treatments relies on the use of biological macromolecules, whose structure offers a high specificity and potency. Unfortunately, due to their complex structure and limited ability to overcome biological barriers, these macromolecules need to be administered via injection. The scientific community has devoted significant efforts to making the oral administration of macromolecules plausible thanks to the implementation of drug delivery technologies. Here, an overview of the current situation and future prospects in the field of oral delivery of biologics is provided. Technologies in clinical trials, as well as recent and disruptive delivery

1 systems proposed in the literature for local and systemic delivery of biologics including
2 peptides, antibodies and nucleic acids are described. Strategies for the specific targeting of
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4 gastrointestinal regions stomach, small bowel and colon, cell populations and internalization
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6 pathways are analyzed. Finally, challenges associated with the clinical translation, future
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8 prospects and identified opportunities for advancement in this field are also discussed.
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11 12 13 14 **1. Introduction**

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16 Precision medicine encompasses treatments targeted to the needs of individual patients on the
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18 basis of genetic, biomarker, phenotypic, or psychosocial characteristics that distinguish a
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20 given patient from other patients with a similar clinical profile.^[1] Hence, its ultimate goal
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22 would be the improvement of the clinical outcomes, with maximized efficacy and minimized
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24 side effects. Accordingly, treatments based on biological [active pharmaceutical ingredients](#)
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26 (APIs) and/or drug delivery technology would intrinsically fall within this concept. Yet, in
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28 different fields of research, the term of precision medicine is being implemented according to
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30 distinctive strategies. For instance, the DIRECT (Diabetes REsearch on patient stratification)
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32 European Initiative is fostering the discovery and validation of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
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34 (T2DM) biomarkers that could help stratify patients for an optimized treatment,^[2] while
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36 efforts to reinforce ‘precision dosing’ in orphan disease and pediatric patients are being
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38 taken.^[3]
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48 In the field of drug delivery, the concept of precision medicine is currently associated with
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50 evolved generations of Drug Delivery Systems (DDS).^[4,5] In this context, two main strategies
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52 for precision treatment, susceptible of being implemented together, could be distinguished
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54 (**Figure 1**); i) enabling the delivery of an API of high specificity, mainly antibody (mAb) and
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56 polynucleotide drugs; ii) targeting the carrier to a specific region or cell population. The
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58 highest expression of this idea is currently envisaged in the area of antitumor therapies, where
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each patient would be treated with a targeted DDS, loading a specific mAb or polynucleotide API selected according to his tumor genetic code^[5].

Figure 1. Precision Medicine in Drug Delivery. Genome mapping and molecular diagnosis techniques allow the identification of disease targets, for which specific biologic drugs and targeting moieties are subsequently designed and/or selected. Drug delivery technologies contribute to precision medicine by designing technologies that i) enable the delivery of biological drugs; ii) target the delivery of non-biological drugs through the functionalized carrier design; or iii) combine both strategies, for the targeted delivery of biological drugs.

In this scenario, regardless of the specific boundaries of the concept of precision medicine, the development of new therapies is inextricably linked to the delivery of biological drugs.^[6]

Essentially, biological drugs including peptides, monoclonal antibodies and nucleic acids offer a much higher specificity and potency than small molecule drugs.^[7,8] However, these

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properties are derived from their large and complex macromolecular structure, which also hampers the preservation of their bioactivity as well as their interaction with biological barriers.^[8,9] As a consequence, these macromolecules need to be administered via injection, while drug delivery technologies are being designed to allow for their administration through alternative routes.

In this context, oral delivery represents a highly attractive modality of administration, both from the patient and from the manufacturing perspective.^[10] Indeed, avoidance of needle-associated pain, higher patient compliance, and non-sterile production requirements are the main advantages offered by this approach. However, the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), naturally designed for compound digestion and processing, constitutes a harsh environment that presents several biological barriers for the absorption of macromolecules. As a consequence, specific drug delivery technologies are mandatory to enable their effective access to their targets.

Hence, the purpose of this review is to analyze the current situation and future prospects on the oral delivery of biologics for precision medicine. To this aim, a brief description of the biological barriers faced in oral administration will be presented. Then, recent advances in oral delivery of biologics, intended to exert their action either locally or systemically, will be commented. Emphasis will be made on the delivery site of the GIT and targeting strategies. Next, current technologies in clinical trials for the oral delivery of biologics will be reviewed. Finally, the challenges identified for the clinical translation of these technologies, as well as a note on future prospects in the field will be discussed.

2. Biological barriers for the oral delivery of biological drugs

The GIT comprises the oral cavity, esophagus, stomach, small intestine and colon. Each of these organs presents heterogeneous properties that must be considered in the design of delivery systems intended to deliver drugs in the different regions of the GIT (**Figure 2**).

Despite its accessibility, the esophagus has only been exceptionally considered a delivery site due to the fast transit time of ingredients administered orally. The stomach on the other side, has been classically regarded as transit region where drugs could be retained and degraded, due to the low pH, presence of gastric enzymes and thickest mucus layer of the GIT.^[7,11] However, other features such as the fact of being the first place for drug delivery, and the fast epithelial regeneration,^[12,13] have led to reconsider its potential. Emerging gastric delivery technologies leveraging from these properties will be commented later.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of GIT sections and their pH, transit time and relevant parameters for drug delivery

The small intestine was traditionally considered the most favorable GIT segment for drug delivery, due to its long transit times, extended surface area, and epithelial permeability followed by systemic absorption.^[11] However, it is not exempt from hurdles to drug delivery such as variable gastric emptying,^[13] degradative enzymes,^[11] complex media composition

1 influencing colloidal stability and drug dissolution,^[14] a protective mucus layer^[15] underlying
2 the epithelium, and the intestinal epithelium itself (**Figure 3**). Once a drug compound, or its
3 loading carrier reaches the intestinal epithelium, four general pathways are identified as
4 potential absorption routes;^[16] i) transcellular pathway through epithelial cells; ii) paracellular
5 pathway in between adjacent cells; iii) transcytosis and receptor-mediated endocytosis,
6 typically through either the hydrogen-coupled peptide transporter (PEOT1), transferring
7 receptor (TfR), IgG neonatal receptor (IgG-FcRn) or through the vitamin B12 uptake
8 pathway;^[17,18] iv) lymphatic absorption through M-cells of Peyer's patches, typically limited
9 to antigen drugs. In addition, upon effective interaction with the epithelium, further
10 mechanisms may decrease the available active dose delivered. Such mechanisms comprise for
11 instance the p-glycoprotein efflux pump,^[19] metabolism by P450 enzymes inside intestinal
12 cells and the liver,^[20,21] and first-pass hepatic effect.^[22]

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29 Finally, the colon provides the materials reaching it with the higher residence time (up to 20h)
30 lower levels of digestive enzymes and bile salts, non-aggressive pH values (6 – 6.7) and lower
31 fluid volumes.^[11,23] On the other hand, transit times and fluid composition present high intra-
32 and inter-individual variability, along with other factors such as the bacteria-rich environment
33 and the presence of stool that may also hamper an efficient drug delivery. Still, it is worth
34 mentioning the high potential of colon-targeted delivery for the local treatment of Intestinal
35 Bowel Diseases (IBD), for which disease-triggered changes in residence time, pH,
36 microbiome, mucus composition and permeability must be taken into account for the design
37 of drug delivery carriers.^[24]

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51 **Figure 3.** Biological barriers for drug delivery at the GIT and delivery mechanisms. [Adapted](#)
52 [with permission.](#)^[25] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

3. Recent advances in preclinical stage on systemic delivery of biological drugs

Most of the technologies described in the literature for the systemic delivery of biological drugs are based on protein and peptide therapeutics, in particular insulin. Even though these molecules do not exactly fall within the definition of precision medicine, they share common characteristics with mAbs and polynucleotides, such as their susceptibility to enzymatic degradation and a polar and hydrophilic complex chemical structure. For this reason, understanding the basis of these technologies could help advance the strategies for both systemic and local delivery of precision medicine drugs.

For a thorough review of peptide systemic delivery systems in clinical trials as well as promising candidates in preclinical stage, readers are encouraged to review the previous works from Aguirre et al.^[26] and Lakkireddy et al.^[25] Meanwhile, this section will focus on the

most recently reported technologies for the delivery of both proteins and polynucleotides (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Recent strategies for oral systemic delivery of biological drugs.

Abbreviations in the figure; HA Hyaluronic acid; γ -PGA poly-gamma-glutamic acid; pArg polyarginine; pSA poly(sialic acid).

3.1. Systemic delivery of protein and peptide drugs through the oral route

3.1.1. Gastric protein and peptide systemic delivery

The most disruptive technologies recently described drew from considering the gastric cavity as a target delivery site instead of the pass-through site it was classically regarded. For example, some technologies have relied on neutralizing the low pH and associated activity of

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gastric enzymes and taking advantage of the fast epithelial repair of the gastric mucosa against potential mild aggressions from formulations.

Buckley et al.^[27] reported a co-formulation of semaglutide, a glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) analog, with the absorption enhancer sodium N-[8-(2-hydroxybenzoyl) aminocaprylate] (SNAC), presented as a tablet. This formulation enabled an average bioavailability of $1.22 \pm 0.25\%$ in dogs and is currently in clinical trials,^[26] however its mechanism was not described in detail until recently. The protection of the peptide against acidic and enzymatic degradation was possible thanks to the buffering capacities of SNAC, which turned the pH of SGF to neutral values. Peptide absorption was mediated through a transcellular route where SNAC would fluidize the membrane of the gastric epithelium cells. This absorption mechanism proved to be compound specific, since interchanging the components by their analogs, liraglutide and *o*-SNAC orthoisomer, markedly decreased this effect. Hence, these findings would encourage the further study of structure-based selection of peptide and penetration enhancer combinations.

Even more recently, another breakthrough technology exploiting the stomach as a delivery site was proposed by Abramson et al.^[28] In this study, a novel administration device preserved the drug loaded in the form of milliposts to be injected into the mucosa. The device consisted of a self-orienting millimeter-scale applicator (SOMA), made of low-density polycaprolactone (PCL) and high-density 316L stainless steel that reproduced the key morphology aspects of the tortoise's shell. In its inner space, a millipost made of compacted insulin is connected to a compressed spring fixed in caramelized sucrose. Upon administration, the device would self-orient its bottom part so as to contact the mucosa, and the gastric fluid would dissolve the sucrose holding the spring, which in turn would inject the miliposts into the tissue. SOMA-aided insulin administration in swine led to similar blood glucose levels

1 and insulin concentrations than s.c. injections. In addition, preliminary successful studies with
2 lysozyme and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, also presented in the same work, highlight
3 the translational potential of the device to other macromolecules.
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9 *3.1.2. Intestinal protein and peptide systemic delivery*

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12 Intestinal delivery of proteins through the use of nanocarriers was first proposed by Couvreur
13 and co. in 1988,^[29] whose approach relied on the association of insulin to
14 poly(alkylcyanoacrylate) nanocapsules. Thereafter, leading experts set the basis for several
15 technological approaches that would influence trends in the field since their inception up to
16 the present. This is the case of the polyanhydride nanoparticles proposed by Mathiowitz et al.
17 in 1997,^[30] the poly(acrylic acid)-g-(ethyleneglycol) (PAA-EG) hydrogels proposed by
18 Peppas et al. in 1999,^[31] and the cell penetrating peptide complexes developed by Morishita et
19 al.^[32] Thereafter, emerging alternative approaches for insulin delivery as well as for other
20 biological APIs arose from the previous knowledge generated in the field (**Figure 5**).
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36 **Figure 5.** Schematic representations of main Drug Delivery Systems technologies and
37 strategies employed for [intestinal](#) delivery of biologics.
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Initially, macro-scaled DDSs (i.e. enteric capsules, pellets, hydrogels) were designed to overcome the degradative gastric environment and to control API release. Later, the advance in the field allowed identifying additional barriers affecting drug delivery (**Figure 3**) and, thus, novel DDSs functionalities were introduced to overcome them. For instance, bioadhesive polymers increased the DDSs residence time at the site of absorption, enzyme inhibitors protected the cargo from degradation, and permeation enhancers facilitated the permeation of drugs either through the paracellular or transcellular route. Overall, these strategies involve the simultaneous release of ^[25] the API and soluble excipients in the intestinal lumen and subsequent transport across the epithelium (Section 2). In contrast, nanoparticulate systems introduced advanced features; due to their smaller size, the system itself could penetrate to deeper regions of the mucus layer or even reach the epithelium, thereby modulating the delivery site and absorption pathway.^[25] Traditionally, these nanosystems consisted of mono-component matrices and were assumed to be translocated upon their interaction with the epithelium, where their size, surface charge and/or targeting moieties dictated the predominating absorption pathway^[33,34] (Section 2). However, advances in the field ^[35–37] are

1 providing new insights that invite to revisit the concepts traditionally established. Specifically,
2 the new generations of oral DDSs (Figure 5) propose multicomponent and dynamic structures,
3 combining several functionalities in the same design, aiming at confronting each of the
4 biological barriers. The elucidation of their multi-step mechanism of interaction with the
5 intestinal epithelium opens up new exciting challenges.
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14 Among these emerging strategies, a previously described microneedle capsule^[38] could be
15 considered the predecessor of the SOMA device, representing also a disruptive concept in
16 intestinal delivery. In this case, the proposed device consisted of a central metallic core from
17 which hollow 25G needles protruded in a radial fashion. The system counted with a pH-
18 sensitive coating that would protect the needles until reaching the intestine. Once there, the
19 outer layer would dissolve and the peristaltic movements would promote the penetration of
20 the needles into the tissue, releasing the drug payload at the submucosal level. As a proof-of-
21 concept of submucosal administration at the GI level, individual serial injections were applied
22 to the intestinal mucosa to Yorkshire pigs, which led to a faster hypoglycemia onset compared
23 to s.c. administration. A new design was proposed that replaced the hollow needles by solid
24 microneedles made of the drug, which were expected to dissolve after injection. An additional
25 technology also based on intestinal injection is the robotic pill from Rani Therapeutics
26 (<https://www.ranitherapeutics.com>). This design is comprised of pH sensitive separate
27 chambers containing citric acid and sodium bicarbonate, along with a balloon-like structure
28 bearing hollow microneedles loaded with peptides. Upon pH increase in the intestine, the
29 acid-base reaction creates CO₂ that inflates the balloon, which in turn pushes the microneedles
30 into the intestinal wall to release the peptides.^[18,22]
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56 A simpler formulation based on the generation of CO₂ to enhance protein absorption was
57 already presented in 2009 under the name of Gas Empowered Drug Delivery (GEDD).^[39]
58 This initial system consisted of a cellulose acetate phthalate (CAP) coated tablet containing
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citric acid and Na-bicarbonate (for CO₂ production), Ac-Di-Sol as super-disintegrant, poly(ethyleneoxide) (PEO) and the permeation enhancer trimethyl chitosan (TMC). *In vivo* studies in healthy rabbits with the GEDD led to conclude that, even though CO₂ may have acted as a mechanical enhancer to open the tight junctions, the presence of both TMC and PEO were necessary for insulin transport across the intestinal membrane. A renewed approach also based on CO₂ generation was recently presented as self-assembled bubble carriers,^[40,41] consisting of an enteric-coated capsule containing the combination of excipients that generate the gas upon dissolution. Specifically, the capsule contained sodium bicarbonate and diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) for CO₂ production, along with the surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS). In this model, SDS was considered critical for absorption, due to its role as bubble stabilization, protease inhibitor and permeation enhancer.

Worth of attention is also the strategy presented by Banerjee et al.,^[42] based on using ionic liquids (ILs) adapted to the oral route. ILs are polar organic solvents constituted by an organic cation and organic/inorganic anion, with a melting point below 100 °C. Specifically, the authors assayed a choline and geranate (CAGE) IL mixed with insulin, where CAGE was expected to interact with amino acid residues of the protein via a combination of hydrophobic and hydrophilic bonds. Upon mixing with intestinal fluids, the interplay between the ions would lead to the formation of micelles or microemulsions. Its mechanism of action was envisaged as a combination of i) maintenance of insulin in its monomeric active form; ii) paracellular permeation enhancement, demonstrated in Caco-2 cells; iii) inhibition of proteolytic enzymes; and iv) mucus layer thinning. Also worth mentioning is the strategy presented as single multiple pill (SmPill[®]),^[43] consisting of enteric-coated emulsion-based minispheres incorporating several permeation enhancers.

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Finally, other strategies recently explored relied on improvements of already described materials^[44–47] and nanocarriers (**Figure 6A, B, C**). In the area of poly(lactic-co-glycolic) nanoparticles (PLGA NPs), a number of functionalized nanoparticles intended to target different molecules and cells in the intestine were developed (**Figure 6A**). For example, Ganugula et al.^[48] synthesized gambogic acid (GA)-functionalized PLGA and produced nanoparticles intended to target the transferrin–transferrin receptor complex (Tf-TfR). In a different instance, Pridgen et al.,^[49] functionalized already formed maleimide-modified PLGA nanoparticles with the targeting ligand IgG Fc, which enabled the targeting of the Fc receptor (FcR). A different approach for the inclusion of targeting moieties in PLGA NPs has made use of chemically modified PEGylated lipids (**Figure 6A**), whose lipid region is inserted into the PLGA matrix, and the ligand-PEG segment is protruding on the external surface of the particles. This is the case of the EGP peptide-functionalized PLGA nanoparticles,^[50] targeting heparan sulfate proteoglycans (HSPGs). The same strategy was adopted^[51] to decorate PLGA NPs with octa-arginine (R8) peptide linked to phosphoserine (PhO). In theory, the brush border intestinal alkaline phosphatase (IAP) would catalyze the hydrolysis of PhO from the nanoparticles surface, hence exposing the cationic R8 residues, which would promote cell uptake.

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Overall, the functionalization of PLGA nanoparticles, first proposed for protein delivery in the early 90's, has led to some of the most promising *in vivo* results in the literature (**Table 1**), while providing valuable mechanistic information on targeting strategies.

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Figure 6A. Chemical structures of main core materials and functionalization strategies of PLGA NPs for precision medicine in oral systemic delivery.

PLGA NPs

Main core component

Polymer backbone / NP surface modification with targeting moieties

Inclusion of targeting moieties through amphiphilic constructs

Abbreviations in the figure; PLGA poly(lactic-co-glycolic); EGP EGP-peptide; DSPE distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylethanolamine; GA gambogic acid; R8 octa-arginine; Pho Phosphoserine.

Chitosan nanoparticles and nanocapsules and their combinations with lipids (chitosan NPs) have also been proposed for oral peptide delivery.^[52-57] The strategy most often applied for their functionalization has involved the chemical modification of the polymer backbone prior to nanoparticle production (Figure 6B). In this regard, recent modifications of chitosan nanocarriers combine the linking of L-valine (LV) for the targeting of intestinal oligopeptide transporters, aiming for improved absorption, along with the inclusion of phenylboronic acid (PBA) intended to induce insulin release in the cytoplasm through reaction with glucose.^[58] TMC NPs were also functionalized with peptide CRTIGPSVC (CRT) in order to target the transferrin/transferrin receptor complex (Tf/TfR), obtaining a 2-fold higher bioavailability

than its counterpart modified with the traditional ligand (HAIYPRH) for the unbound TfR.^[59] Other modifications of chitosan nanoparticles **without chemical modification of the core polymer** include their coating with thiolated hyaluronic acid (HA-SH) to facilitate mucodiffusion^[60] and with poly(γ -glutamic acid) (γ -PGA) NPs in order to target the apical sodium-dependent bile acid transporter (ASBT).^[61] These modifications led to a 1.9- and 2.2-fold increase in bioavailability respectively, when compared to their non-modified counterparts.

Figure 6B. Chemical structures of main core materials and most relevant modifications in recent designs of chitosan NPs for precision medicine in oral systemic delivery.

Abbreviations in the figure; TMC trimethyl chitosan; OPM oleyl-PEG-mannose; γ -PGA gamma-polyglutamic acid; HA-SH thiolated hyaluronic acid; CMCS-PBA-LV carboxymethyl chitosan-phenylboronic acid-L-valine; MTC mannose-modified trimethyl chitosan-cysteine conjugate..

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2 With regard to lipid-based nanosystems, Prat et al. found that conveniently designed
3 nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) could induce GLP-1 secretion from enterocytes.^[62] Other
4 authors have proposed [new lipid nanocarrier designs based on their coating or the inclusion of](#)
5 [additional components with added functionalities \(Figure 6C\)](#). For instance, Xu et al.^[63]
6 proposed the inclusion of an endosomal escape agent, peptide GLFEAIEGFIENGWEGMIDG-
7 WYG (HA2), in solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN), while other authors explored coating
8 exendin-4 (Ex- 4)-loaded liposomes with chondroitin sulfate-g-glycocholic acid (EL-CSG),
9 with the purpose of targeting the bile salt pathway.^[64] Finally, polymeric lipid-based
10 nanocapsules such as poly(arginine) (pArg)^[65] and polysialic acid (pSA)/protamine
11 nanocapsules,^[66] were recently proposed for insulin oral delivery by Alonso et al. These
12 nanosystems combine the properties of lipid and polymeric materials, i.e. the penetration
13 enhancing properties of arginine-rich polymers.

14 [Figure 6C. Chemical structures of main core materials and most relevant modifications in](#)
15 [recent designs of lipid-based nanoparticles \(lipid-based NPs\) for precision medicine in oral](#)
16 [systemic delivery.](#)

Lipid-based NPs

Main core component

Inclusion of components for added functionalities

GLFEAIEGFIENGWEGMIDGWYG HA2 peptide

Surface coatings

Protamine

PRRRRSRPVRRRRRRRRRRVSRRRRRRRGRRRR

pArg

Chondroitin sulfate-g-glycocholic acid

Abbreviations in the figure; HA-SH thiolated hyaluronic acid; γ -PGA poly(γ -glutamic acid); pArg poly(arginine); pSA polysialic acid.

Finally, advances in the area of penetration enhancers are worth mentioning. These compounds are the basis of most formulations currently in active clinical evaluation (section 5), probably fostered by their less complex design as compared to other types of DDS. In addition, increasing knowledge on their mechanistic and compound specificity is being gathered.^[67,68] Aside from the gastric enabled delivery with SNAC (Section 3.1.1), most relevant recent contributions of penetration enhancers for intestinal delivery are worth mentioning. Mrsny and col. aimed at regulating an endogenous paracellular pathway for dietary macromolecules as entry pathway for therapeutic proteins.^[69] To do so, they synthesized *de novo* peptides chemically designed to reach the cytoplasm of enterocytes, and successively modulate the phosphorylation of an intracellular regulatory complex (MLCP)

mediating the TJ barrier. Accordingly, the peptides structure was based on i) a sequence emulating the regulatory subunit (CPI-17) of the MLCP complex; ii) basic aminoacids emulating cell penetrating peptides sequences (CPP) to allow for membrane permeability; and iii) arranging the included D-aminoacids in reverse orientation for increased stability. From the resulting family of Permeant Inhibitor of Phosphatase (PIP) peptides, selected candidates were assayed for their permeation enhancer capability in co-administration with insulin in rats, and the results showed bioavailability values up to 1.6%.

Finally, an evolved model based on the CPPs researched by Morishita and co.^[70] was recently proposed in the form of nanocarriers by Niu et al.^[37] Instead of co-administrating the CPP and the therapeutic protein, the authors designed a core-shell nanostructure by complexing insulin and hydrophobically modified R8, and further coating it with a pegylated protective polymer. The resulting nanocarriers exhibited a massive accumulation in intestinal epithelial cells, but a fairly modest *in vivo* response. This was attributed to a slow release of the protein from the nanocomplexes accumulated at the intestinal epithelium, which hence highlighted their potentially more advantageous utility for the local delivery of intestinally acting peptides.

Table 1. Recent nanotechnologies for the intestinal targeted systemic delivery of peptide drugs -2015 – at present-.

DRUG	DDS	IN VIVO RESULTS	Year of publication	Ref.
Model proteins sCT, urokinase, and rituximab	pH-responsive P(IA-co-NVP)) and enzymatically-degradable hydrogels of P(MAA-co-NVP)*	N/A	2016	[71]
GLP-1, DPP-4	(CPP-modified chitosan)-coated PLGA and pSi NPs, loaded into HPMC matrices*	N/A	2015	[72]
GLP-1, DPP-4	Chitosan-modified pSi NPs, loaded into HPMC matrices**	N/A	2015	[73]
Peptide U2, U5, SOD, OM, α – Lact, Lyz, STI	Lycopodium clavatum spores (sporopollenin exine capsules, SECs) loaded into alginate microgranules**	1.45 \pm 0.19% BA	2017	[74]
Insulin	poly (glutamic acid)-poly (ethylene glycol) (PGA-PEG) enveloped octaarginin (r8)-peptide nanocomplexes	20% maximum blood glucose	2018	[37]
Insulin	Fc-Targeted PLGA NPs	13.7 \pm 1.3%*hour NP-Fc BA. Blood glucose decrease up to 45%	2013	[49]

1	Insulin	EGP peptide modified PLGA NPs	5.62% BA	2018	[50]
2	Insulin	DSPE-PEG-R8 and DSPE-PEG-Phosphoserine coated PLGA NPs	5.96% BA	2018	[51]
3					
4	Insulin	Gambogic acid (GA)-functionalized PLGA NPs	32.70% BA	2017	[48]
5					
6	Insulin	Tf-functionalized PLGA-poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) NPs	40% maximum blood decrease	2016	[75]
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8					
9	Insulin	Core-shell HA-coated insulin-L-penetratin NPs	11% BA	2018	[76]
10					
11	Insulin	Deoxycholic acid-chitosan - γ -p(glutamic acid) (DS-CS- γ -PGA) NPs	15.9% BA	2018	[61]
12					
13	Insulin	Carboxymethyl chitosan/chitosan-nanoparticles (CMCS/CS-NPs)	>15% BA	2017	[77]
14					
15	Insulin	L-valine (LV) and phenylboronic (PBA) modified chitosan NPs	7.55 \pm 1.32% BA	2017	[58]
16					
17	Insulin	Thiolated hyaluronic acid (HA-SH)-coated modified chitosan NPs	11.3% BA	2018	[60]
18					
19	Insulin	CRT-peptide-modified trimethyl chitosan (TMC) NPs	6.84% BA	2017	[59]
20					
21	Insulin	SLNs with HA2 peptide endosomal scape co-encapsulated	5.47% BA	2018	[63]
22					
23	Exenatide, liraglutide	Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs)	No effect	2018	[62]
24	Insulin	Polyarginine Nanocapsules (pArg NCs)	2.14% BA	2017	[65]
25					
26	Insulin	Protamine Nanocapsules (Prot NCs)	20% maximum blood glucose	2016	[66]
27					
28	Exendin-4 (Ex4)	Chondroitin sulfate-g-glycocholic acid-coated liposomes (EL-CSG)	19.5 \pm 2.0% BA	2019	[64]
29					
30	Insulin	SAR6EW (CPP) coated CS-TPP-insulin NPs	50.7% maximum blood glucose	2017	[78]
31					
32	Insulin	PLGA and folic acid modified chitosan (PLGA/FA-CS) nanocarriers	7.22% BA	2017	[79]
33					
34	Insulin	Trimethyl chitosan-coated PLGA NPs (MNPs) loaded with insulin-low molecular weight protamine (LMWP) conjugates	17.98 \pm 5.61% BA	2016	[80]
35					
36	Insulin	L-cys or CPP-modified CS-conjugated silicon NPs	6.2 \pm 1.9% BA	2016	[81]
37					
38	Insulin	Thiomaly chitosan (TCS) NPs	1.5% BA	2015	[82]
39					
40	Exendin-4 (Ex4)	Aqueous drug-micelles core lipid-based NPs	12.7 \pm 4.5% BA	2014	[83]
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42					

* Microsystem; ** Nanosystem loaded into [Microsystem](#). Abbreviations in the table; BA

Bioavailability; sCT Salmon Calcitonin; CPP Cell Penetrating Peptide; CAP Cellulose Acetate Phtalate; pSi silicon; Phe Phenylalanine; Ala Alanine; Cys Cysteine; SOS Superoxide dismutase; OM Ovomuroid; α -Lact α -Lactalbumin bovine, Lyz Lysozyme, STI Soybean trypsin inhibitor; BSA Bovine Serum Albumin; N/A non available. For further information on

oral systemic delivery technologies for protein and peptide drugs published before 2015, readers are encouraged to refer to the works of Aguirre et al.^[26] and Lakkireddy et al.^[25]

3.2. Systemic delivery of nucleic acid drugs through the oral route

The number of technologies described for the systemic delivery of polynucleotide drugs through the oral route is scarce as compared to that referring to protein/peptide drugs (Table 2). This could be due to the later advancement of this delivery area and, hence, future works in this direction are expected.

A multi-responsive technology was developed recently, combining bacteria engineering and nanotechnology for a systemic tumor treatment. Specifically, Fan et al.^[84] employed thermally sensitive programmable bacteria (TPB), by transforming noninvasive bacterium *E. coli* MG 1655 with a plasmid pBV220 containing a thermally sensitive promoter and TNF- α gene. Subsequently, the TPB was further decorated with photothermal gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), obtaining TPB@Au. The idea behind this technology is that, upon oral administration, TPB@Au would protect the cargo in the gut and transport it through transcytosis by the M cells. Once in circulation, the bacteria would accumulate preferentially at tumor sites due to the anaerobic environment. Finally, remote control would trigger the generation of heat from AuNPs by near-infrared (NIR) light radiation, which in turn would activate the temperature-sensitive expression of TNF- α . Systemic internalization of the bacteria in mice after oral administration was confirmed by plate colony counting and imaging techniques, and its antitumor effect evaluated with positive results.

A number of synthetic nanosystems has also been prepared for the systemic delivery of polynucleotides. For instance, a modification of CS consisted of a mannose-modified trimethyl chitosan-cysteine (MTC) conjugate,^[85] able to form NPs with TNF- α siRNA by

1 ionic gelation (MTC NPs). The mannose, cysteine and thiol residues were expected to allow
 2 overcoming the extracellular and intracellular barriers to oral siRNA delivery. The NPs were
 3
 4 able to protect mice with acute hepatic injury from inflammation-induced liver damage and
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 6 lethality, by inhibiting TNF- α production in macrophages after oral administration. Direct
 7
 8 CLSM observation after oral administration of TAMRA-siRNA MTC NPs confirmed the
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 10 systemic absorption and macrophage uptake of the NPs.
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 14 A further chitosan-based carrier targeting the same application through oral delivery of TNF- α
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 16 siRNA consisted of supramolecular self-assembled nanoparticles (SSNPs),^[86] comprised of
 17
 18 several building blocks. Each component played a key role in the system; oleyl trimethyl
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 20 chitosan (OTMC) would provide enhanced permeation and gene transfection; the cationic
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 22 peptide poly(γ -(4-(((2-(piperidin-1-yl)ethyl)- amino)methyl)benzyl-L-glutamate) (PVBLG-8)
 23
 24 would promote cellular internalization and endosomal escape; oleyl-PEG-mannose (OPM)
 25
 26 would improve macrophage uptake by targeting mannose receptors; and oleyl-PEG-
 27
 28 cysteamine (OPC) would improve mucoadhesion through disulfide bonds with mucin
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 30 glycoproteins from mucosa and cell surfaces. The result of the oral administration of TNF- α
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 32 siRNA SSNPs to acute hepatic injury mice model was an anti-inflammatory effect with a
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 34 relative pharmacological bioavailability of 10 %.
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44 **Table 2.** Recent technologies for the systemic delivery of nucleic acid drugs

GI target section	Disease	Drug	Type of DDS	DDS	Year of publication	Ref.
Intestine	Acute hepatic injury	TNF- α siRNA	Nanosystem	Mannose-modified trimethyl chitosan-cysteine conjugate NPs	2013	[85]
Intestine	Acute hepatic injury	TNF- α siRNA	Nanosystem	PEGylated trimethyl chitosan-(modified polyglutamate) NPs (OTMC/TPP/PVBLG-8/OPM/OPC)	2013	[86]
Intestine	Cancer	TNF- α plasmid	Nanosystem	Au NPs-decorated plasmid-containing thermally responsive bacteria (TPB)	2018	[84]

Abbreviations in the table; OTMC Oleyl Trimethyl Chitosan (OTMC); TPP Tripolyphosphate; PVBLG cationic peptide poly(γ -(4-(((2-(piperidin-1-yl)ethyl)-amino)methyl)benzyl-L-glutamate)); OPM Oleyl-PEG-Mannose; OPC Oleyl-PEG-Cysteamine.

4. Technologies for the local oral delivery of biological drugs

In parallel with the technology solutions for the treatment of systemic diseases, considerable efforts have been made to develop oral technologies to deliver biologic drugs (**Figure 7**) that exert local action in the GIT. Up to date, most of the work has focused on colon-targeted delivery for the treatment of IBD, i.e. ulcerative colitis (UC) and Crohn's disease (CD), where nanotechnology appears to hold promise.

Other [gastrointestinal \(GI\)](#) targets for local therapy include the small intestine and the stomach. While less research has been conducted to treat gastric diseases using biological drugs, there is a growing interest in oral vaccination targeting small intestinal M cells in the gut-associated lymphoid tissue of the Peyer's patches.

Figure 7. Current oral strategies to treat local diseases in the stomach, small intestine and colon.

4.1. Gastric delivery

Although a vast number of gastric delivery systems have been developed to prolong the drug retention time in the stomach and to enhance drug solubility at low pH condition, most of them have been applied to small molecules (e.g. antibiotics). In recent years, to improve therapeutic specificity and reduce side effects, new precise medicines have been investigated using biological drugs. Protein-based solutions have been explored to address gastric diseases such as infection, ulcers and cancers. For instance, Kennedy et al. conjugated a modified human Fab protein to the PEGylated PLGA NPs. The 300 nm nanoparticles were able to specifically recognize and target the CD44v6 expressing cells in tumor sections. Considering the overexpressing of CD44v6 in gastric and colorectal cancer, this work showed potential for diagnosis and treatment of relevant carcinoma.^[87]

1 In an effort to treat gastric cancer, Caspase-3 was loaded into an ultrasound-propelled gold
2 nanowire coated by a pH-responsive polymer (Eudragit L30 D-55). The nanosystem was
3 investigated in a human gastric adenocarcinoma cell model, and the results showed an
4 efficient and fast apoptosis.^[88]
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9 Biological approaches relying on the use of recombinant Lactobacillus suspension and
10 platelet-rich human plasma have been used respectively to treat gastric infection and gastric
11 ulcer. The Helicobacter pylori urease B (UreB) produced by Lactobacillus was shown to
12 provide partial protection against Helicobacter felis infection,^[89] the vascular endothelial
13 growth factor (VEGF) released from platelet remarkably accelerated gastric ulcer healing.^[90]
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23 **4.2. Intestinal delivery**

24 *4.2.1. Proteins and peptides*

25 *Oral vaccination*

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28 Protein and peptide therapeutics have been principally used for vaccination targeting the small
29 intestine, and for the alleviation of IBD in the colon. [Although, strictly speaking, an oral
30 vaccine might not be considered as a precision medicine](#), as it does not apply to a specific
31 population segment, the antigen delivery carriers are designed to target a specific cell
32 population, which are the M cells of the Peyer's patches (**Figure 8**).^[91] To induce an immune
33 response, antigens have to overcome the enzymatic degradation along the GIT, cross the
34 mucus layer that stretches over the mucosal surfaces and penetrate the epithelium. Adequate
35 delivery systems such as nano and micro sized carriers offer interesting possibilities in this
36 regard (**Table 3**). There are examples in the literature showing the capacity of poly[(methyl
37 methacrylate)-co-(methyl acrylate)-co-(methacrylic acid)] (PMMMA) and PLGA NPs
38 (**Figure 9A**) loaded with a surface immunogenic protein (SIP) and B Streptococcus (GBS), to
39 deliver them to the colon of tilapia fish. This oral vaccine resulted in the production of high
40 levels of SIP specific antibodies and induced robust immunity against GBS infection.^[92] To
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prevent diarrhoeal infections, Davitt et al.^[93] utilized Single Multiple Pill® (SmPill®) oral vaccine formulation with an enteric polymer coating to protect the colonization factor antigen I (CFA/I), JT-49 in the GIT environment (α -galactosylceramide as adjuvant). This formulation enhanced CFA/I-specific immunoglobulin A (IgA) responses in the intestinal mucosa in addition to serum IgG. In a study aimed at comparing the immunization effect targeting small intestine versus large intestine,^[94] peptide antigen (PeptAg)-loaded PLGA NPs were embedded into microparticles with a Eudragits® L100-55 or Eudragits® FS30D coat to achieve small/large intestinal pH-dependent release, respectively. Following oral delivery to mice, the colon-targeted system induced colorectal immunity and protected against both, rectal and vaginal, viral challenge. In contrast, the formulation targeting small intestine only induced mucosal immunity in the small intestine.

Figure 8. Illustration of oral vaccination achieved by transcellular pathway across the M cells of the Peyer's patches or paracellular pathway across the intestinal epithelium in the small intestine

Overall, current research has addressed the possibility to treat local and systemic diseases through oral vaccines. Antigens packaged within delivery systems are better recognized by

the immune system and are able to induce stronger immune responses than soluble antigens. Useful strategies have been developed to target the intestinal membrane and enhanced the antigen uptake by immune cells. However, despite the large number of effective mucosal vaccines in animal models (principally mice), the clinical trials have often failed, due to the poor immunogenicity.^[95] New effective adjuvants are being developed to solve this problem.^[95] At this time, oral vaccines already launched include Vaxchora® (PaxVax) for cholera, Vivotif® (Crucell) for typhoid, Rotarix® (GSK) and RotaTeq® (Merck) against rotavirus, and Adenovirus Type 4 and Type 7 Vaccine (no trade name yet) for acute febrile respiratory disease (www.fda.gov/biologicsbloodvaccines/vaccines/approvedproducts/ucm093833.htm).

However, the first 3 candidates are based-on live-attenuated organisms, and the last 2 are live virus. Only a few commercialized vaccines use protein-based antigens (e.g. virus-like particles, detoxified toxins, polysaccharide-protein conjugates), while none have been developed yet for oral application.

Table 3. Intestine-targeted delivery of peptides and proteins for oral vaccination.

GI Target	Action	Biologic Drug	Type of formulation	Composition	Ref.
Intestine	Local + systemic	Contents of tumor-cell microparticles	Cell derived vesicles	Tumor cell-derived microparticles	[96]
Colon	Local	Surface immunogenic protein	Nanosystem	PMMMA-PLGA NPs	[92]
Colon vs. Intestine	Local + systemic	Peptide antigen (PeptAg)	Nanosystem in Microsystem	Eudragit® FS30D/L100-55 microparticle loaded with PLGA NPs	[94]
Intestine	Local	Ovalbumin (OVA)	Nanosystem	Mannan-modified pH-responsive P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels	[97]
Intestine	Local	Chicken egg OVA and cholera toxin sub- unit B as antigens	Mixture of antigen	Recombinant unlipidated outer membrane protein from Brucella spp. (U-Omp19)	[98]
Intestine	Local	Synthesized antigenic peptides	Synthesized peptide	Chemically synthesized highly stable antigenic peptides	[99]
Intestine	Local	OVA	Microsystem	Pollen grains	[100]

Intestine	Local + systemic	Colonization factor antigen I (CFA/I), JT-49	SmPill®	SmPill with whole cell killed E. coli overexpressing colonization factor antigen I (CFA/I), JT-49 and adjuvant α -galactosylceramide	[101]
Intestine	Local + systemic	Tumor-associated antigen Her2/neu	Nanosystem	Chitosan and functionalized PLGA NPs	[102]
Intestine	Local + systemic	OVA	Microsystem	OVA-KFE8 nanofiber/ CaCO ₃ composite microparticles	[103]
Intestine	Local + systemic	Bovine serum albumin (BSA)-FITC	Microsystem	Aminopeptidase N-targeted β -glucan microparticles	[104]
Intestine	Local + systemic	M-BmpB protein, i.e. M cell-homing peptide (CKSTHPLSC)	Microsystem	Thiolated hydroxypropyl methylcellulose phthalate	[105]
Intestine	Local + systemic	OVA, BSA	Microsystem	Calcium carbonate- and mannitol-templated porous microspheres	[106]
Intestine	Local + systemic	Membrane protein B of Brachyspira hyodysenteriae (BmpB)	Microsystem	CKS9-conjugated water-soluble chitosan-coated BmpB-loaded PLGA MPs	[107]
Intestine	Local + systemic	OVA	Microsystem	β -glucan particles	[108]
Intestine	Local + systemic	MvP728-survivin with GSL1	Fused gene protein	Tumor-associated antigens fused with genes of Salmonella pathogenicity island 2	[109]
Intestine	Local	Claudin 4-targeting peptide incorporated Influenza hemagglutinin recombinant protein	Nanosystem	PLGA NP	[110]

Abbreviations in the table; PMMMA poly[(methyl methacrylate)-co-(methyl acrylate)-co-(methacrylic acid)]; P(HEMA-co-MAA) poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate-co-methacrylic acid).

Intestinal local delivery of peptides and proteins

Proteins and peptides have been used to improve small intestinal local conditions such as infection, [diarrhoea](#), enzyme deficiency and injury. For instance, Wu et al.^[111] sought to deliver anthelmintic protein Cry5B to the small intestine as protection against parasitic infection using mesoporous silicon particles. In another work, heparin-binding EGF-like epithelial growth factor (HB-EGF) was embedded into a custom designed polyglycolic acid/polylactic acid scaffold for small intestinal tissue regeneration.^[112] When implanted on site, HB-EGF was slowly released in an active form and led to the formation of tissue-engineered intestinal mucosa in rat.

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In addition to the treatment of small intestinal diseases, peptides and proteins-based therapies have been also used for the treatment of IBD. The most common colonic delivery strategies applied to biological drugs have been functionalized PLGA NPs (Figure 9A)^[113,114] and hydrogel-based system.^[115,116] A range of these systems has shown their therapeutic potential in animal models. For example, Leoni et al.^[114] encapsulated exogenous annexin A1 mimetic peptide (Ac2-26) into PEG-PLGA NPs for the treatment of IBD-related chronic mucosal injury. For specifically reaching the injured mucosa and vessels, these nanoparticles were surface-modified with a collagen IV-targeting heptapeptide ligand.^[117] The local delivery of these functionalized nanoparticles (Ac2-26 Col IV NPs) to the colon of colitis-induced mice accelerated the epithelial wound repairing. Xiao et al.^[113] used hyaluronic acid-functionalized PLGA NPs (in a chitosan/alginate hydrogel) to selectively deliver the drug, lysine-proline-valine tripeptide (KPV), to inflamed target cells and address ulcerative colitis. These systems relieved inflammation in the colon, prevented mucosa damage and mitigated body weight loss following oral administration. In a different approach, Yan et al.^[115] showed that a bacteria-derived p40 protein could activate EGFR and lead to Akt activation, whereby inhibiting the cytokine-induced apoptosis in intestinal epithelial cells. They loaded p40 protein in hydrogel beads composed of a gastrointestinal resistant polysaccharide pectin and zein, a gastric stable hydrophobic protein for oral administration. The formulation showed potential to prevent and heal colonic injury and acute colitis in a mouse model.

Figure 9. Structures of representative materials involved in local delivery of biologics, including functionalized PLGA and chitosan (A) and others (B).

(A) Chemical modification of PLGA and chitosan for local delivery of biologics

(B) Other representative materials for local delivery of biologics

Abbreviations in the figure; PMMMA Poly[(methyl methacrylate)-co-(methyl acrylate)-co-(methacrylic acid)]; Col IV Collagen IV-targeting ligand; v6 Fab Fab protein that target human CD44v6; GTC Galactosylated Trimethyl Chitosan; CKS9 an M cell homing peptide; PMAA-co-NVP Poly(methacrylic acid-co-N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone); PPADT Poly-(1,4-phenyleneacetone dimethylene thioketal); DEAEEMA 2-(diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate; PEI Polyethylenimine; T-HPMCP thiolated hydroxypropyl methylcellulose phthalate

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2 However, up to date, only a few small peptides with good stability and high potency have
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4 reached the market or the clinical development se. For instance, Vancomycin (Vancocin®,
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6 ANI Pharmaceuticals), a glycosylated tricyclic heptapeptide (1.4 kDa) is being marketed as a
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8 drug for diarrhoea and enterocolitis, while more analogues are under clinical trials. Another
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10 short chain peptide Linaclotide (Linzess®, 1.5 kDa, Ironwood pharmaceuticals/Allergan) is
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12 currently in the market for irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) and constipation, and a number of
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14 similar drugs are in clinical trials. For more information please refer to the section 5 of this
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16 review. Moreover, pancreatic enzyme product such as Creon® (Abbvie) has been marketed to
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18 relieve the digestive enzyme deficiency due to pancreatitis.
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26 *4.2.2. DNA and RNA*

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28 Nucleic acids, particularly siRNAs, have been extensively researched to treat IBD and colonic
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30 cancer over the last decades, as alternatives to conventional therapy such as small molecular
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32 drugs (e.g. anti-inflammatory drugs, immune suppressors, antibiotics) and surgery. The vast
33
34 majority of these biologic drugs are delivered using nanotechnology. **Table 4** summarizes the
35
36 representative approaches based on the use of nanotechnology, for colon and small intestine-
37
38 targeted DNA/RNA delivery via oral route. Overall, polysaccharides and polyamines such as
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40 chitosan, alginate, [modified cationic cyclodextrin](#) and polyethylenimine (PEI, **Figure 9B**) are
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42 the biomaterials more frequently used to build nanocarriers and hydrogels because they
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44 provide resistance to the gastric and small intestinal enzymes (eg. protease, peptidase and
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46 lipase). Specificities about illustrative nanocarriers reported in the last years are reported
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58 McCarthy and co-workers^[118] developed nanocomplexes between TNF- α siRNA and
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60 modified amphiphilic cationic β -cyclodextrin. Their local administration to mice rectum
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1 induced a significant reduction in both colon weight loss and colonic mRNA expression of
2 TNF- α and IL-6, together with a mild improvement in clinical signs of colitis. Zuo et al.^[119]
3
4 formulated nanocomplexes of galactosylated low molecular weight chitosan and antisense
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6 oligonucleotide to relieve experimental colitis. The intracolonic treatment in mice reduced the
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8 expression of inflammatory cytokines, improved the body weight loss, intestinal protein loss
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10 and diarrhoea, and revealed a great amelioration in clinical sign and histopathological severity
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12 of the disease. In an effort to promote RNA interference^[120], epigallocatechin-3-O-gallate
13
14 (EGCG), a natural polyphenol from green tea was used to facilitate the complexation between
15
16 prolyl hydroxylase 2 siRNA and a series of cationic polymers. Among the groups, the
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18 siRNA-EGCG-polylysine nanocomplexes showed lowest cytotoxicity, potential to down-
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20 regulate target genes both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, and efficiently ameliorated chronic intestinal
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22 inflammation in mice.
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29 In addition, nanoparticles have been rationally synthesized as encapsulation systems of
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31 nucleic acids to relieve diseases of the large intestine. Wilson et al.^[121] loaded TNF- α siRNA
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33 into nanoparticles formulated with poly-(1,4-phenyleneacetone dimethylene thioketal)
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35 (PPADT), a polymer that degrades in response to the high levels of reactive oxygen species
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37 (ROS) at the inflammation site in the colon. Oral gavage of these nanosystems showed the
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39 capacity to decrease TNF- α mRNA level in an ulcerative colitis mouse model.
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44 Knipe and co-workers^[122] prepared 2-(diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate (DEAEMA) (**Figure**
45
46 **9B**) based nanogels that swell at early endosomal pH (~5.5), to facilitate the endosomal
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48 escape and deliver TNF- α siRNA to the cytosol of macrophages in the inflamed intestinal
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50 region. These nanogels were entrapped into microgels made of poly(methacrylic acid-co-N-
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52 vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (PMAA-co-NVP) (**Figure 9B**) crosslinked by a trypsin-degradable
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54 peptide for gastric protection and intestinal release.
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59 In another rational design, Xiao et al.^[123] loaded CD98 siRNA into 200 nm nanoparticles
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61 comprising modified chitosan, urocanic acid, PEI and PEG to facilitate the mucus
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transportation (PEG), cellular uptake (chitosan; PEI) and endosomal escape (urocanic acid).

The nanosystems were functionalized with single-chain CD98 antibody to target the colonic epithelial cells, and then entrapped into a hydrogel composed of chitosan and alginate to avoid the gastrointestinal digestion before reaching the inflamed site in the colon. Following oral gavage to mice with colitis, it was found that these nanoparticles were taken up by the colonic macrophages and that the expression of CD98 was reduced. The syndrome of colitis was improved in terms of the loss of body weight, myeloperoxidase activity, inflammatory cytokine production and histological analysis.

A different approach was chosen by Zhang et al.^[124] who made nanoparticles from edible ginger, containing lipids, proteins, 125 miRNAs, and other constituents (6-gingerol and 6-shogaol). These nanoparticles showed intestinal epithelial cell and macrophage uptake with limited cytotoxicity. Oral administration to mice with colitis led to the proliferation of intestinal epithelial cells, decreased the pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-1 β) and increased the anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10 and IL-22). The treatment enhanced intestinal repairing and prevented chronic colitis and colitis-associated cancer. In a follow-up work from the same group^[125], ginger-derived lipids were used to generate nanoparticles to load CD98 siRNA and the oral administration led to reduced expression of CD98.

In the last years, new and more sophisticated technologies have been used in RNA-based therapies for intestinal diseases. In an effort to treat colon cancer, Conde et al.^[118] conjugated Avastin® (Bevacizumab, VEGF inhibitor) to gold nano-rods (4x10 nm) and conjugated anti-*Kras* siRNA to gold nanospheres (20 nm), both embedded into an adhesive hydrogel patch consisted of dextran-poly(amidoamine) G5 dendrimer and dextran aldehyde for implantation adjacent to the tumor. Following the knockdown of oncogene driver *Kras* by siRNA, near-infrared radiation was applied in order to trigger the localized Avastin® release and stop cancer cell proliferation, while, at the same time, its heat induced cell damage. The gene

therapy, chemotherapy and phototherapy involved in this formulation synergistically led to a complete tumor regression, showing an advantage over systemic administration or intratumoral injections in terms of tumor shrinkage and survival rate.

Table 4A. Local delivery of nucleic acids following oral administration for the treatment of IBD. Asterisk (*) indicates the non nano-based approach.

GI Target	Biologic Drug	Composition	Ref
Colon	TNF- α siRNA	Fab'-bearing PLA-PEG NPs loaded in chitosan (CS)-alginate gel	[126]
Colon	CD98 siRNA	scCD98- functionalized UAC/CS/PEI/PEG NPs in CS/alginate hydrogel	[123]
Colon	TNF- α siRNA	Mannose-functionalized p(CBA-bPEI) – Tripolyphosphate (TPP) NPs	[127]
Colon	Prolyl hydroxylase 2 siRNA	Low molecular weight (MW) cationic polymer-EGCG-siRNA core-shell NPs	[120]
Colon	CD98 siRNA	Ginger-derived lipid vehicles	[125]
Colon	Anti TNF- α , KC or IP-10 siRNA	PEI-coated PLGA NPs loaded with calcium phosphate-siRNA NPs (multishell NPs)	[128]
Colon	CD98 siRNA	HA-modified CS-coated PLGA NPs encapsulating siRNA and curcumin, loaded in an alginate/CS hydrogel	[129]
Colon	Cleaved oligonucleotide	DNA-functionalized gold NPs encapsulated into primary isolated intestinal stem cells	[130]
Colon	Chemically modified TNF- α siRNA	Chemically modified TNF- α siRNA	[131]*
Colon	TNF- α siRNA	Thioketal NPs	[121]
Colon	IL-10-producing plasmid DNA	Gelatin NPs in poly(epsilon-caprolactone) microsphere matrix	[132]
Colon	TNF- α siRNA	Nanocomplex of siRNA and modified cationic β -cyclodextrin	[118]
Colon	Map4k4 siRNA	Galactosylated trimethyl chitosan-cysteine NPs	[133]
Colon	NF-kB decoy oligonucleotide	CS-modified PLGA nanospheres	[134]
Colon	Antisense oligonucleotide against TNF- α	Complex between galactosylated low MW chitosan and antisense oligonucleotide	[119]
Colon	pcDNA3-EGFP	Phosphorylated CMC-G6P and PEI-polyarginine conjugates NP	[135]
Intestine & colon	125 miRNAs	NPs derived from edible ginger (GDNPs 2)	[124]

Intestine & colon	TNF- α siRNA	P[MAA-co-NVP] microgel, cross-linked by a trypsin-degradable peptide linker	[122]
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Abbreviations in the table; UAC urocanic acid; PEI polyethylenimine; CBA cystamine bisacrylamide; TPP sodium triphosphate; EGCG epigallocatechin-3-O-gallate; PMAA-co-NVP poly(methacrylic acid-co-N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone).

Table 4B. Colon and small intestine-targeted delivery of nucleic acids for cancer treatment.

GI Target	Biologic Drug	Composition	Ref
Colon	Small active RNA	PEI/p21-RNA-322 polyplex core with HA modulated lipid shell	[136]
Colon	β -catenin siRNA	PEGylated CS NPs	[137]
Colon	hSET1 asRNA	CS and thiolated carboxymethyl dextran complexes	[138]
Colon	DNA duplex (model DNA therapeutic)	NIPAAm-co-AAm hydrogel with near-infrared absorbing silica-gold nanoshells	[139]
Colon	siRNA	PEGylated PEI-lipid NP	[140]
Colon	Avastin® (Bevacizumab) and <i>Kras</i> siRNA	Adhesive dextran-poly(amidoamine) G5 dendrimer hydrogel scaffold containing functionalized gold nanorods and gold nanospheres	[141]
Intestine	asRNA (Gapmers)	CS NP	[142]

Abbreviations in the table; HA hyaluronic acid; NIPAAm-co-AAm poly(N-isopropylacrylamide-co-acrylamide); P[MAA-co-NVP] poly(methacrylic acid-co-N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone); CMC-G6P carboxymethyl cellulose-glucosamine 6-phosphate.

Overall, considerable efforts have been recently made to achieve the targeted delivery of anti-TNF biologics to the inflammatory site of IBD. The result of such treatments has been a relief of the symptoms and a reduction of the disease progression. A combined strategy of chemical modification and enteric coating, Mongersen (Celgene Ltd), an antisense oligonucleotide have reached clinical phase for the treatment of Crohn's disease (NCT02596893) and UC (NCT02601300). In addition, Alicaforsen (Atlantic Pharmaceuticals Ltd), a phosphorothioate-

modified antisense oligonucleotide has been indicated in the clinical treatment of pouchitis (NCT02525523).

It should be highlighted that although biologics have been shown to suppress the inflammatory process in many IBD patients, their response may vary from individual to individual. In this scenario, personalized medicine becomes critical for the correct use of these therapies.^[143] During medication, more parameters (eg. biologic, endoscopic and histologic) have been used to monitor the status of diseases, and the remote care of patients by telecommunications (telemedicine) has been found useful to improve the medical adherence and therapeutic outcome. Accordingly, clinical trials are becoming more personalized to reach this unmet need. The characteristics of an individual patient and the profile of each disease have been taken into consideration for more accurate diagnosis, prognosis and choice of drug.

4.2.3. Bacteria

The use of commensal human bacteria is an emerging strategy of potential interest for the treatment of intestinal local diseases (Table 5). Their mechanism of action relates to the functionality of metabolites produced by these microbiotas or to their own genome DNA after arrival to the inflamed sites. This approach has been considered particularly suitable for long-term management of local diseases in the colon and intestine.

Table 5. Bacteria-based strategies for the treatment of intestinal local diseases.

GI Target	Disease	Bacteria	Property of bacteria	Ref
Colon	IBD	Modified <i>L. lactis</i>	<i>L. lactis</i> that secretes Trefoil Factors (TFF)	[144]
Colon	IBD	Modified <i>L. lactis</i>	<i>L. lactis</i> that secret low calcium response V protein (LcrV)	[145]
Colon	IBD	Modified <i>B. ovatus</i>	<i>B. ovatus</i> that produces human keratinocyte growth factor (KGF)-2 (together with dietary xylan)	[146]
Intestine	Cholera	Native or modified <i>L. lactis</i> strains	Native <i>L. lactis</i> that produces lactic acid; Engineered <i>L. lactis</i> that can detect and report on <i>V. cholerae</i> presence	[147]

1	Intestine	Cholera	Modified <i>V. cholerae</i>	Modified <i>V. cholerae</i> strains by deleting the diarrhoeagenic factors (HaitiV)	[148]
2					
3	Colon	IBD	Probiotic VSL-3 or their isolated DNA; or <i>E.coli</i> DNA	Nonviable/viable probiotics VSL-3 (4 lactobacilli strains, 3 bifidobacteria strains, 1 streptococcus strain); Or their native/metabolised DNA; Or <i>E.coli</i> DNA	[149]
4					
5					
6	Colon	IBD	Modified <i>L. lactis</i>	Genetically engineered <i>L.s lactis</i> that secretes IL-10	[150]
7					
8	Colon	IBD	Modified <i>E. coli</i>	Engineered non-pathogenic invasive <i>E.coli</i> that expresses invasin	[151]
9					
10					
11	Colon	Cancer	Modified <i>E. coli</i>	Engineered <i>E. coli</i> strains, capable of invading tumour cells (InvColi)	[152]
12					
13	Intestine	Influenza (vaccine)	Modified <i>E. coli</i>	Engineered <i>E.coli</i> that expresses invasin	[153]
14					
15					
16	Intestine	IBD	Engineered <i>L. lactis</i>	Engineered <i>L. lactis</i> that synthesizes immunosuppressive IL-27	[154]
17					
18	Colon	IBD	Engineered <i>L. lactis</i>	Engineered <i>L. lactis</i> that secretes monovalent and bivalent murine (m)TNF-neutralizing nanobodies	[155]
19					

Abbreviations in the table; *L. lactis* *Lactococcus lactis*; *E. coli* *Escherichia coli*; *B. ovatus*

Bacteroides ovatus; *V. cholerae* *Vibrio cholerae*

Lactococcus lactis (*L. lactis*) has been genetically modified to secret different bioactive proteins and peptides. Vandembroucke et al.^[144] developed food-grade *L. lactis* that could produce trefoil factors (TFF), a class of non-mitogenic peptides responsible for intestinal epithelium protection and repairing. Following intragastric administration, the modified *L. lactis* could effectively reach the colon and actively produce TFF *in situ*. This strategy was successfully used to prevent acute colitis. Similarly, Foligne et al.^[145] engineered *L. lactis* species capable of producing low calcium response V (LcrV), a bioactive protein that could block the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α , IFN γ , and promote the generation of anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10. Oral administration of this bacteria resulted in the active production of LcrV in the colon, and subsequent colitis prevention in mice. With the same purpose, *L. lactis* was also modified to secret IL-10 and IL-27.^[150,154] Other bacteria employed for this approach are genetically modified *Bacteroides ovatus* (*B. ovatus*) and non-pathogenic invasive *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), which contributed to treating IBD,^[146,151] colon cancer^[152] or were used for vaccination^[153] in animal models successfully. In a clinical study, genetically

1 modified *L. lactis* that secretes anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10 has been packaged in enteric
2 capsules for ulcerative colitis treatment, however, the study failed to pass Phase II in 2009
3
4 (NCT00729872). Similarly, genetically modified *E. coli* that express β -catenin silencing short
5
6 hairpin RNA is currently under Phase I/II clinical trial as treatment for familial adenomatous
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8 polyposis.
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14 Based on a different theory, the possibility to attenuate intestinal diseases using probiotics has
15
16 also been investigated. According to the World Health Organization and the Food and
17
18 Agriculture Organization, probiotics are live microorganisms that confer a health benefit to
19
20 the host when administered in adequate amounts.^[156] Their mechanisms of action involve the
21
22 modification of the gut flora by producing antimicrobial substances, competition with
23
24 pathogenic bacteria, modulation of mucosal immune responses, regulation of luminal acidity
25
26 and improvement of the intestinal barrier function.^[157,158] As an example, Mao et al.^[147]
27
28 employed native *L. Lactis* able to produce lactic acid to suppress cholera, given the fact that *V.*
29
30 *cholerae* is especially sensitive to an acidic environment. In another attempt to fight cholera,
31
32 Hubbard et al.^[148] developed a non-diarrhoeagenic *V. cholerae* strain for vaccine use. These
33
34 live bacteria mediated a probiotic-like protection in infant rabbits. Rachmilewitz et al.^[149]
35
36 administrated intragastrically viable/non-viable probiotics VSL-3 (a blend of 8 probiotics) or
37
38 their isolated native/metabolized DNA to mice with experimental colitis. Both, live and dead
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40 probiotics, as well as native probiotic DNAs ameliorated the severity of experimental colitis.
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42 Further studies suggested that this probiotic-induced healing effect is mediated by toll-like
43
44 receptor 9 (TLR9) signaling. There are plenty of probiotic products in the market that are
45
46 claimed to alleviate IBS, IBD and/or [diarrhoea](#) caused by infection or antibiotics, nevertheless,
47
48 their pharmacological benefits are yet to be clinically demonstrated.
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61 **5. State of oral delivery technologies of biological drugs in clinical trials**

A number of products already in the market are preceded by an enticing amount of delivery technologies under clinical evaluation, for both systemic and local delivery (**Figure 10**). These technologies were thoroughly reviewed previously by Aguirre et al.,^[26] Moroz et al.^[159] and Richard et al.,^[18] whose work we encourage readers to review for further mechanistic and composition details. Updated information on their development stage can be found in **Table 6a,b**. Consequently, in this section attention will be focused on new technologies joining the clinical landscape, along with new relevant information from technologies previously identified.

Figure 10. Oral drug delivery technologies for biologics marketed or in clinical trials.

Updated and adapted with permission.^[26] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

As shown in **Table 6a**, the majority of marketed products contain small lipophilic peptides and the formulation approaches are based on physical mixtures of permeation enhancers and

enzymatic inhibitors combining enteric coatings. The nanocarriers are represented by calcium phosphate nanoparticles, silica nanoparticles and liver targeted liposomes.

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Table 6a. Technologies marketed or in clinical trials for oral systemic delivery of biological drugs.

Company - Technology/Product	Indication	Protein/ Peptide/ polynucleotide	Strategy	Phase	ClinicalTrial.gov Identifier
Novartis AG (Switzerland) Neoral®/ Sandimmune®	Immunosuppression	CsA	Self-emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems (SNEDDS)	Marketed	-
Ferring Pharmaceuticals (Switzerland)/ Generic products (e.g. Actavis Labs FL Inc., NJ, USA) DDAVP® Tablets DDAVP® Melt Minirin®	Central <i>Diabetes Insipidus</i> , Primary Nocturnal Enuresis	Desmopressin acetate hydrate (DDAVP)	Chemical modification	Marketed	-
Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma Corporation (Japan) Ceredist® Ceredist OD®	Spinocerebellar degeneration	Taltirelin hydrate	Chemical modification to avoid enzymatic hydrolysis	Marketed	-
Theranaturals Inc. (ID, USA) Reduced L-Glutathione	AIDS-related cachexia/cystic fibrosis	Glutathione	None	Marketed	-
NOD Pharmaceuticals, Inc. (China) NOD/Nodlin™	Diabetes	Insulin	Nanoparticles with a calcium phosphate core and pegylated salts of fatty acids, coated with carbomer and cellulose acetate phthalate	I	ChiCTR-TRC- 12001872*
Oshadi Drug Administration Ltd. (Israel) Oshadi lcp	Diabetes	Insulin	Silica-based nanoparticles	II	NCT01973920
Diasome Pharma (OH, USA) HDV-I	Diabetes	Insulin	Liver-targeted liposomes	III	NCT00814294
Merrion Pharmaceuticals Ltd. (Ireland) with Novo Nordisk A/S (Denmark) Insulin 320 (NN1957)	Diabetes	Insulin	PE: sodium caprate	I	NCT02479022
Insulin 338/ GIPET® I/ OI338GT (NN 1953)	Diabetes	Insulin		II	NCT02470039
NNC0113-0987 (NN9926)/ OI338GT	Diabetes	GLP-1 analog		I	NCT02094521
GIPET®/ ACY-7/ MER-104	Prostate cancer, male oral contraception	Acyline		I/II	NCT00603187
Oramed Pharmaceuticals, Inc. (Israel) POD™/ ORMD 0801	Diabetes	Insulin	PEs: EDTA, bile salts Enzyme inhibitors: soy bean trypsin inhibitor, aprotinin	II	NCT03467932

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21	Proxima Concepts Ltd (UK)/ Bone Medical Ltd	Diabetes	Insulin	PE: aromatic alcohols	II	2005-004753-95**
22	(Australia)/ Diabetology (UK)					
23	Axess™ / Capsulin™/					
24						
25	Capsitonin™ (BN002)/	Osteoporosis	sCT		III	N/A
26						
27	CaPTHymone™ (BN003)/ Perthoxal™	Osteoporosis	PTH		II	N/A
28						
29						
30	Enteris Biopharma, Inc. (NJ, USA)	Endometriosis	Ovarest® (oral leuprolide	PE. Acyl carnitine/ pH modulator, CA/	II	NCT02807363
31	Peptelligence™		tablet)	Peptide with D-stereochemistry		
32				resistant to proteases (Cara)		
33						
34		Chronic Kidney Disease	KORSUVA™		II	NCT03617536
35		(CKD) associated	(CR845/difelikefalin)			NCT02524197
36		pruritus, chronic pain				NCT02944448
37						
38						
39	Emisphere Technologies, Inc. (NJ, USA) with	Diabetes	Insulin	PE: N-acylated alpha-amino acid	I	NCT00982254
40	Novo-Nordisk (Denmark)			(undisclosed)		
41	Eligen®/ Novo insulin candidate					
42	Eligen®NN9924/OG217SC	Diabetes	Semaglutide (long-acting GLP-	PE: Sodium N-[8-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)	III	NCT03021187
43			1)	Amino] Caprylate (SNAC)		NCT03015220
44						NCT02906930
45						NCT02863419
46						NCT02849080
47						NCT02773381
48						NCT02692716
49						NCT02607865
50	Emisphere Technologies, Inc. (NJ, USA) with Nordic	Osteoporosis	sCT (SMC021)	PE: 8-(N-2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-	III	NCT00525798
51	Biosciences (Denmark) and Novartis (Switzerland)			amino- caprylic acid (5-CNAC)		NCT00486434
52	Eligen®					NCT00704847
53	Sigmoid Pharma (Ireland)	Immunosuppression	CsA	Oil in water emulsion	I/II	NCT01033305
54	SmPill®/ CyCol™					
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56	Tarsa therapeutics, Inc. (PA, USA)/ Enteris	Osteoporosis	sCT	Local pH modulator: CA		NDA approved for
57	Biopharma, Inc./ R-PHARM JSC					review (2016)
58	Peptelligence™/ TBRIATM					
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Chiasma, Ltd. (Israel) TPE®/ Mycapssa™	Acromegaly	Octreotide	PE: sodium caprylate	III	NCT03252353 NCT02685709 NCT01412424
Biocon Ltd (India) IN-105/ Insulin Tregopil	Diabetes	Insulin-alkylated PEG prodrug insulin conjugates	Chemical modification	II/III (did not meet endpoints)	NCT03430856

PE: penetration enhancer; CsA cyclosporine; sCT salmon calcitonin;. *Chinese Clinical Trial Registry (www.chictr.org.cn); **EU Clinical Trials Register (www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu)

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2 The peptide-based locally acting marketed formulations consist mainly of peptides of around
3
4 1-2kDa molecular weight with a cyclic structure, which makes them resistant against
5
6 peptidase degradation. In order to enable local delivery of larger macromolecules, new
7
8 emerging technologies came also into play in the clinical scenario, several of them based on
9
10 chemical engineering designs of the drug itself. For instance, the company Protagonist
11
12 Therapeutics, Inc. developed Vectrix™, a proprietary peptide drug discovery platform,
13
14 consisting of molecular design tools and libraries of scaffolds. This platform allows designing
15
16 peptide structures to achieve the desired features,^[160] by identifying disulfide rich peptides
17
18 (DRP)-based hits and leads. As a result, highly constrained and stable chemical entities are
19
20 obtained, combining the advantageous properties of both mAbs and small molecule drugs.
21
22 The company currently counts with two GI-restricted peptides in clinical trials
23
24 (<https://www.protagonist-inc.com>); PN-10-943 for UC, which achieved Phase II evaluation;
25
26 and PTG-200 for the treatment of CD. The later completed Phase 1 evaluation, and Phase 2a
27
28 is expected, according to the company webpage. The company entered into an agreement with
29
30 Janssen Biotech, Inc. for further co-development of the candidate.
31
32 Following a similar rationale, Avaxia Biologics, Inc. (<http://avaxiabiologics.com>) developed
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34 Avaximabs™, a gut-targeted antibody platform inspired in the properties of milk-derived
35
36 polyclonal antibodies. The company developed first AVX-470, a milk-derived antibody
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38 naturally able to survive in the GIT, which is now in Phase I for UC treatment. The company
39
40 identified the structural basis for the ability of milk-derived antibodies to survive in the GIT,
41
42 and transferred the key attributes to a recombinant platform. Their first engineered candidate
43
44 was Avaximab™-TNF, an orally-delivered anti-TNF antibody for the treatment of IBD.
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46 Avaximab™-TNF implemented the optimized features of stability against intestinal digestion,
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48 minimal systemic exposure, penetration into inflamed gut mucosa and potential ability for
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50 local activation of effector functions.
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1 An alternative technology has been presented by VHSquared (www.vhsquared.com), under
2 the name of Vorabodies™. A Vorabody is an oral domain antibody engineered to enhance
3 intestinal protease resistance. Their leading compound is V565, an oral anti-TNF α Vorabody,
4 capable of inhibiting inflammation in UC patients.^[161] The final oral dosage form comprised a
5 capsule containing enteric-coated minitabets loaded with V565.^[162] In the stomach, the
6 capsule dissolves and releases the minitabets, which then travel along the intestine and
7 release the Vorabody at pH > 6. The authors reported very low systemic exposure of the drug
8 in healthy monkeys. This candidate is currently in Phase II clinical trials (**Table 6b**,
9 NCT02976129).

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21 Protalix Biotherapeutics introduced the ProCellEx® delivery platform, by using plant cells as
22 a natural oral delivery vehicle for proteins (<http://protalix.com>). Upon administration, the
23 cellulose wall of these natural carriers protects the recombinant proteins from degradation
24 along the GIT. The company counts with several candidates in clinical evaluation (**Table 6b**),
25 delivering; pegunigalsidase alfa for the treatment of Fabry disease in Phase III; a recombinant
26 human tumor necrosis factor receptor II fused to an IgG1 Fc domain (TNFRII-Fc) for UC in
27 Phase II; and the glycosylated glucocerebrosidase enzyme (prGCD) for the treatment of
28 Gaucher disease also in Phase II.

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41 A similar rationale was followed by the company Intrexon (<https://www.dna.com>), in their
42 technology ActoBio Therapeutics™ (<https://actobio.com>). The technology consists of an
43 attenuated food grade *Lactococcus lactis* genetically modified to secrete a therapeutic protein
44 drug, formulated in an enteric capsule. Specifically for intestinal delivery, two main
45 candidates are currently in Phase I/II clinical trials (**Table 6b**); AG014, which secretes
46 certolizumab for the treatment of GI symptoms in primary immunodeficiency (PID) patients;
47 and AG019, secreting human proinsulin autoantigen (hPINS) and tolerance-enhancing
48 cytokine hIL-10, for the treatment of early onset of type 1 Diabetes.

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Regarding the use of polynucleotides for intestinal local delivery, only a few technologies are currently in clinical evaluation. This is probably due to the late advancement in the oral nucleic acids delivery field and, hence, more technologies are expected to reach clinical evaluation in the near future. The technologies leading the way in the clinic are based on enteric coatings and drug chemical modifications to improve the stability against degradation. This is the case of the candidate Monarsen from BioLineRx (<http://www.biolinerx.com>), an antisense oligonucleotide (AON) chemically modified for improved stability. Initially, this drug was developed by Amarin Corporation for the treatment of myasthenia gravis with limited success. Later, the molecule was reported to have an anti-inflammatory off-target effect, which led BioLineRx to further develop it as an oral treatment for UC, so far obtaining positive results in Phase II (**Table 6b**). The candidate Mongersen from Celgene (<https://www.celgene.es>), currently in Phase II/III for the treatment of Ulcerative Colitis and Crohn's disease, was developed following the same rationale. Finally, a bacteria-based platform for local delivery of polynucleotides also reached clinical trials. Adhera Therapeutics (<https://adherathera.com>), formerly Marina Biotech, developed a transkingdom RNA interference platform (tkRNAi) based on genetically modified *E. coli*. Their most advanced candidate is CEQ508, currently in Phase I/II. In this candidate, the genome has been altered to allow for whole bacterium endocytosis by the epithelial cells, while expressing and delivering β -catenin silencing short hairpin RNA for the treatment of adenomatous polyposis.

Table 6b. Technologies marketed or in clinical trials for oral local delivery of biological drugs.

Company - Technology/Product	Indication	Protein/ Peptide/ polynucleotide	Formulation Strategy	Phase	ClinicalTrial.gov Identifier
ANI Pharmaceuticals, Inc. (MN, USA) Vancocin®	Infection	Vancomycin HCl	None, cyclic structure	Marketed	-
Biocon Ltd. (India) Koolistin®	Infection	Colistin sulfate	None	Marketed	-
Several Several brands (lozenge)	Pharyngitis	Tyrothricin	None	Marketed	-
Cubic Pharmaceuticals/ Merck	Infection	Surotomyacin	None, lipopeptide, cyclic structure	III	NCT01597505NC T01598311
Nanotherapeutics	Infection	Ramoplanin	Lipoglycodesipeptide, cyclic structure	IIb	N/A
Novartis	Infection	LFF-571	Chemical modification, cyclic structure, thiazolyl peptide	II (removed from pipeline)	NCT01232595
Novacta Biosystems Limited	Infection	NVB302	None, cyclic structure, thioether bonds	I	N/A
Acatavis, Inc. (NJ, USA) /Ironwood Pharma, Inc. (MA, USA) Linzess® (USA) Constella® (Europe)	IBS, CIC	Linaclotide	None, cyclic structure	Marketed	-
Synergy Pharmaceuticals Inc. (NY, USA) Uroguanylin analog	Opioid-induced constipation (OIC) and UC	Dolcanatide (SP-333)	Chemical modification, cyclic structure	II	NCT01983306
Uruguanylin analog	OBS, CIC	TRULANCE®/ Plenacatide		NDA fillings	-
Abbvie Creon®	Exocrine pancreatic insufficiency	Porcine protease, amylase, lipase	Enteric coated capsules	Marketed	-
Protagonist Therapeutics, Inc./ Janssen Biotech, Inc. Vectrix™	CD	PTG-200	Chemical structure designed for improved functionality and stability	I	N/A

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21	Avaxia Biologics, Inc.	UC	-	-	I	NCT01759056
22	AVX-470 (milk-derived anti-TNF polyclonal antibody)					
23						
24	Avaxia Biologics, Inc./ Circle33 LLC	IBD	Avaximab™-TNF	Antibody recombinant platform based on the properties of milk-derived antibodies	-	-
25	Avaximabs™					
26						
27	VHsquared Ltd.	UC	V565 (anti-TNF α domain antibody)	Antibody domains engineered to resist enzymatic degradation, loaded in enterically coated mini-tablets	II	NCT02976129
28	Vorabodies™					
29						
30						
31	Protalix Biotherapeutics	Fabry disease	Pegunigalsidase alfa (PRX-102)	Plant cell-based platform producing recombinant therapeutic proteins	III	NCT03018730
32	ProCellEx®					NCT02795676
33						NCT02921620
34						NCT03614234
35						NCT03180840
36						NCT03566017
37		UC	OPRX-106 (recombinant human tumor necrosis factor receptor II fused to an IgG1 Fc domain (TNFRII-Fc))		II	NCT02768974
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39						
40		Gaucher disease	Glycosylated glucocerebrosidase enzyme (prGCD) (PRX-112)		II	NCT02107846
41						
42	Intrexon (formerly ActoGeniX)	GI symptoms associated to primary immunodeficiency (PID)	Certolizumab, anti-TNF α Fab fragment (AG014), capsule in combination with enema	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> genetically modified to secrete a therapeutic peptide/protein in enteric capsule	I/II	N/A
43	ActoBio Therapeutics™					
44						
45						
46						
47		Early onset of type 1 Diabetes	Autoantigen human proinsulin (hPINS) and tolerance-enhancing cytokine hIL-10/ AG019		I/II	NCT03751007
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51	BioLineRx	MG, UC	AON targeting TNF- α mRNA a pathologic mRNA splicing variant of AChE	Chemical modification (aqueous solution)	II	NCT01506362
52	Monarsen/ EN 101/ BL-7040					
53						
54	Celgene	CD; UC	AON targeting Smad7 protein mRNA	Chemical modification, enteric coated formulation	II/III	NCT02596893
55	Mongersen/ GED-0301/ BL-7040/ EN101					NCT02601300
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57						
58	Adhera Therapeutics (formerly Marina Biotech)	Adenomatous polyposis	β -catenin silencing short hairpin RNA	Genetically modified <i>E. coli</i> for whole endocytosis at epithelium	I/II	N/A
59	tkRNAi platform/ CEQ508					
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MG Myasthenia Gravis; IBS Irritable Bowel Syndrome; CIC Chronic Idiopathic Constipation; UC ulcerative colitis; CD Chrohn's Disease (CD);

IBD Inflammatory Bowel Disease; AON Antisense Oligonucleotide.

6. Challenges to the clinical translation of oral drug delivery of biologics

In order for a technology to make the transition from bench to bedside, controlled design and performance, robustness, safety, scalability, and favorable cost/benefit ratio are mandatory. A simplified drug delivery design,^[23] and the use of excipients that were either already in approved products or regarded as GRAS,^[11] has been the common guideline for the development of the formulations, currently in clinical trials. However, these incremental drug delivery approaches seem to have reached a top limit in its performance. For instance, a 1-2% systemic bioavailability has been generally reported for macromolecules in clinical settings.^{[26][163]} Hence, more complex designs are taking the lead, following the current trends in the drug delivery field.^[163] A first step in this direction is represented by formulations still based on well-known materials in the form of multi-component nanosystems, such as recent lipid-based nanocarriers.^[47] Another trend follows bio- inspiration, such as incorporating chemical modifications from naturally occurring molecules or pathogen mimicking features, as described above. Finally, further complex technologies comprise full *de novo* chemical synthesis of drugs and polymers, cell-based delivery systems, smart pills, or even combinations of these. These emerging strategies raise concerns not only from the toxicological and regulatory point of view,^[164] but also regarding their cost, scale-up feasibility, and controlled performance.^[163,165] More complex designs require the definition and evaluation of a higher number of quality attributes, which may imply a higher challenge when modifications of the formulation are needed for scaling-up and translation. In this sense, steps forward are currently being taken in a common effort from researchers, industry and regulatory agencies, especially in the area of nanotechnology. For instance, a ‘minimum information standard’ for bio-nano systems (MIRIBEL, Minimum Information Reporting in Bio Nano Experimental Literature) was recently proposed as guidance,^[166] and the increasing

1 presence of nano-based technologies in the clinic in recent years^[163,167] is, at the very least,
2 encouraging.
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7 In line with this effort, oral delivery technologies may also benefit from standardization and
8 knowledge sharing within the scientific community. For instance, agreement on uniform
9 preclinical *in vitro* and *in vivo* testing conditions might allow for a wider comparison of
10 technologies and the identification of optimum features. This could apply to the very early
11 stages of formulation development, where the design is optimized according to the stability,
12 release and behavior in cell culture. In addition, different *in vivo* settings, even though assayed
13 in a same animal model, such as administration route (oral gavage, intestinal injection or *in*
14 *situ* intestinal loop), use of anesthesia, fasting time and the employment of grid floors to avoid
15 coprophagy,^[168–170] may highly influence the actual *in vivo* conditions for delivery. Last but
16 not least, already established differences in length, morphology, pH, fluid content and
17 composition, motility and histology between animal models and humans^[171–176] could be
18 translated into experimental guidelines. Implementing procedures for the *in vitro* assessment
19 and adaptation of a formulation from small to large animal models, and eventually humans,
20 could hence contribute to the technological advancement of the field.
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43 An ultimate constraint specific for oral administration is imposed by the need to generate a
44 final solid dosage form. In the first place, this frequently requires a freeze-drying step for
45 formulations produced in an aqueous-based media.^[177] This step implies the addition of high
46 concentrations of cryoprotectants and risks the maintenance of the bioactivity of the
47 macromolecule, compromising the final active loading of the formulation. At this point,
48 evaluating the preserved bioactivity of the loaded drug^[178], as well as maintained *in vitro*
49 performance of the formulation after the drying process is recommended. Secondly, the
50 maximum dimensions tolerated for an oral dosage form physically impedes the amount of dry
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1 powder formulation that can be loaded.^[7] Therefore, the initial drug loading of the
2 formulation, need of freeze-drying and consequent amounts of cryoprotectant included, final
3 active dose delivered, and expected bioavailability range should be altogether considered
4 from the initial stages of development.
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9 Finally, the *in vivo* evaluation of the final dosage form may lead to additional difficulties for
10 translation. Rodent animals are by far the most employed models in preclinical evaluation.
11 While large-scale smart devices may not be miniaturized and assayed in this model, gelatin
12 minicapsules offer a relatively widely employed option for powder formulations.^[40] However,
13 the highly variable, size and shape dependent gastric emptying^[169,179] should be taken into
14 account for DDS targeted to the intestine. Unfortunately, similar constraints regarding gastric
15 emptying and transit times remain in large animal models.^[172,180]
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26 We are aware that implementing commonly-shared standards in early technology
27 development, encompassing tools for overcoming all the identified translational hurdles, is a
28 very ambitious and challenging request. However, as the field advances, more knowledge in
29 formulation development and in how to overcome biological barriers is generated. In this
30 sense, we would encourage sharing negative results, especially those obtained in advanced
31 stages of development. We are overall confident that secure steps are being taken in the right
32 direction.
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43 44 45 **7. Concluding remarks**

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47 The advances in genome mapping and molecular diagnosis are enabling the development of
48 precision medicine. The development of successful treatments involves not only the discovery
49 of new therapies but also their adequate delivery to their targets. In this context, oral delivery
50 of macromolecules remains being a highly challenging endeavor, due to the GIT restrictive
51 biological barriers. If we take into account that the first attempt to administer insulin orally
52 was carried out in the 1920s and that, so far, there are not marketed oral formulations
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1 containing such large molecules, this enterprise may seem highly disappointing. However, the
2 field has undeniably evolved; new biological and translational barriers have been discovered
3 and strategies to overcome them provided. Several formulations are currently in advanced
4 clinical trials and disruptive novel technologies, questioning previously established ideas,
5 have been proposed. It is our view that oral delivery of biologics is a realizable approach, yet
6 it is a much more demanding task than predicted. We believe that future steps to continue to
7 advance the field must rely not only on novel designs, but also on the standardization of
8 preclinical parameters and procedures, integrative technology designs considering
9 translational aspects, and knowledge sharing, especially that originated from negative results.
10 It is our hope that all these factors will continue to be addressed as a common effort by the
11 academia and industry communities along with regulatory agencies.
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